

Monitoring and communicating co-occurring forest disturbance processes using Earth Observation data

Vasco M. Mantas¹, Elsa Baltazar¹, Jorge Canhoto¹, Alcides J.S.C. Pereira¹, M. Jozefiak², N. Lewyckyj³

¹ University of Coimbra, Portugal; ² S[&]T, Norway; ³ VITO, Belgium

vasco.mantas@dct.uc.pt

CONTEXT

Pine Wilt Disease
Pinewood nematode
Pine sawyer beetle

First detection in Europe: 1999¹

B. xylophilus
causal agent

+

Monochamus galloprovincialis
vector insect

Affected area
infects (in Portugal) predominantly *Pinus pinaster*

SOLUTION

Multilayered solution

- Space (Sentinel-2/Landsat-8/WV-3)
- Airborne (APEX)
- UAV (multi- & hyperspectral)
- field and laboratorial analysis

Artificial Neural Network

outputs:
Land use land cover
Symptomatic trees
Physiologic status

User needs

RESULTS

Medium Resolution

(Sentinel-2, accuracy: 93%)

10 000 training pixels 10x10 m
Field validated training data
850 spectral samples
100 trees monitored monthly
ANN implemented in python

high
low
probability

Very High Resolution results

(WV3 algorithm, accuracy: 92%)

year 1

year 2

year 3

• symptomatic trees (field-validated)

Dissemination

www.silvisense.com

FOCUS
budget: ~2 M USD
Horizon 2020 (GA776026)

1. Mota, M.M., Braasch, H., Bravo, M.A., Penas, A.C., Burgermeister, W., Metge, K., Sousa, E., 1999 First report of *Bursaphelenchus xylophilus* in Portugal and in Europe, *Nematology*, 1, pp. 727-734.